

Densities and apparent molar volumes for glycine, DL- α -alanine and β -alanine for water and water + (1, 3, 5 and 7 M) urea solutions at 288.15, 298.15 and 308.15 K

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Densities (ρ) of glycine, DL- α -alanine and β -alanine in water and water + urea solution have been measured with Anton Paar DMA60/601 model for calculation of apparent molar volumes (V_ϕ). The data were regressed against concentration to determine limiting values (V_ϕ^0) of molar volume and used to evaluate limiting apparent transfer volumes ($V_\phi^0(\text{tr})$) of systems from water to water + urea, and methylene (CH_2) and $\text{N}^+\text{H}_3\text{COO}^-$ contribution to V_ϕ^0 . Likewise $V_\phi^0(\text{tr})$ data were used to calculate the combined ($2V_{\text{AU}}$) and triplet ($3V_{\text{AUU}}$) interaction coefficients of acids to explain dipolar interactions. The V_ϕ^0 values of β -alanine are seen slightly higher than of DL- α -alanine and of glycine than urea for aqueous systems.

Precise ρ of glycine and urea for water, and glycine¹⁻³, DL- α -alanine, β -alanine and many other amino acids for water + urea are of current interest⁴⁻⁶ for apparent molar volumes. Which is an elegant tool to elucidate the structural behavior of amino acids in mixed solvents at various temperatures⁷⁻⁹. As glycine, DL- α -alanine and β -alanine are considered as model amino acids and hence apparent and limiting molar volumes in aqueous and aqueous urea^{8,9} systems explain thermodynamics of dipolar interactions¹⁰⁻¹⁶. Likewise investigation on contribution of covalent and ionic character of acids for apparent molar volume is useful for hydrophilic¹⁷⁻¹⁹ and hydrophobic interaction²⁰⁻²² studies. Similarly the transfer in V_ϕ^0 for glycine from water to water + urea is fascinating the scientists engaged in protein research as it is helpful to calculate the interaction coefficients^{23,24} and degree of electrostriction proteins in aqueous and mixed solvents. Although V_ϕ^0 of glycine for water + 3 m urea solutions²⁵ is measured at 298.15 but the studies for 7 m urea are not undertaken at 288.15 and 308.15 K. Likewise the studies on DL- α -alanine and β -alanine for water + urea are undertaken at 288.15, 298.15 and 308.15 K to estimate an influence of urea composition and thermal energy on dipolar interactions. Because the composition and temperature of urea do affect the structure of protein and biopolymers significantly for biological and biophysical control therefore the studies on the monomers of protein systems are focused.

Results and discussion

Densimeter was calibrated with natural vibration period

(τ) of OT for air and water at desired temperature from relation,

$$\rho_a = A\tau^2 + B \quad (1)$$

$$\rho_w = A\tau^2 + B \quad (2)$$

By solving eqs. (1) and (2), the constants A and B are calculated from relations,

$$A = (\rho_{\text{water}} - \rho_{\text{air}})/(\tau_{\text{water}}^2 - \tau_{\text{air}}^2)$$

$$B = (\tau_{\text{air}}^2 \rho_{\text{water}} - \tau_{\text{water}}^2 \rho_{\text{air}})/(\tau_{\text{water}}^2 - \tau_{\text{air}}^2)$$

The ρ_{water} , ρ_{air} water, air densities, and τ_{water}^2 and τ_{air}^2 are vibration periods. An air density (ρ_{air}) at any desired temperature can be calculated from a relation,

$$\rho_{\text{air}} = \frac{0.001293}{1 + 0.00367 t^2} \quad (3)$$

The t^2 is air temperature, the relation is based on Van der Waals equation for real gases²⁶ and ρ of water is taken from literature²⁷, and of systems was obtained from relation,

$$\rho_{\text{soln}} - \rho_{\text{water}} = A (\tau_{\text{air}}^2 - \tau_{\text{water}}^2) \quad (4)$$

The solutions were introduced to OT with needle fitted to a disposable polyethylene syringe of 2 cm³ capacity and an oscillation constant A of tube was measured for solution as well as solvent. The calibration is made with the ρ values of glycine and urea standard solutions with precision of 3×10^{-6} g cm⁻³. The densities ($\pm 4 \times 10^{-5}$ g cm⁻³) for aqueous NaCl solutions^{27,28} were measured and apparent molar volume was calculated with ± 0.14 cm³ mol⁻¹ uncertainty and is found in close agreement of literature, the values are

Table 1. Densities ($\rho^0 \pm 0.00002$) and limiting apparent molar volumes ($V_\phi^0 \pm 0.02$) for urea and glycine in water fitted to a linear regression eqns.

T (K)	Urea in water		Glycine in water		NaCl in water	
	V_ϕ^0 $\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$	$A \pm 0.03$	V_ϕ^0 $\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$	$A \pm 0.03$	V_ϕ^0 $\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$	$A \pm 0.03$
288.15	44.21 (± 0.13)	0.11	42.49 (0.12)	0.96	15.11	2.40 ^a
298.15	44.24 (± 0.12)	0.11	43.26 (± 0.6)	0.78	15.12	2.39
298.15	44.23 (± 0.11)	0.12	42.90 (± 0.6)	0.78	16.45	1.97 ^a
303.15	44.63 (± 0.10)	0.01	43.90 (± 0.7)	0.65	16.47	1.93
308.15	44.91 (± 0.09)	0.08	43.60 (± 0.12)	0.65	17.39	1.65 ^a
308.15					17.39	1.63
313.15	44.94 (± 0.11)	0.04	44.06 (0.11)	0.06		

^aRef. 27.

Fig. 1. Y-axis V_ϕ^0 in $\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$ and X-axis molality of urea $m \text{mol kg}^{-1}$ of solution (*Ref. 8).

given in Table 1. Similarly the ρ of systems are used to determine apparent molar volumes (V_ϕ) with relation,

$$V_\phi = \frac{1000(\rho_0 - \rho_s)}{m \rho_0 \rho_s} + \frac{M}{\rho_s} \quad (5)$$

where ρ_0 and ρ_s are densities of solvent and solution, m and M molality and molar mass of solute. The ρ and V_ϕ data have been found to be a function of concentration and ρ of urea solutions as cosolvent was determined by regressing the values against composition from relation,

$$\rho = \rho^0 + S_d m \quad (6)$$

Notably the ρ^0 values extrapolated to zero composition of

Fig. 1a. The V_ϕ^0 vs m for glycine in aqueous urea solutions at 298.15 K: (o) Ogawa in 3 m urea, (•) Exp. in 3.0619 m urea.

urea were used for calculation of V_0 of acids in ternary systems. Likewise V_ϕ data were treated as,

$$V_\phi = V_\phi^0 + S_v \sqrt{m} \quad (7)$$

The m is molality of solution but V_ϕ^0 is limiting apparent molar volume and S_v is slope constant and are given in Table 2, similarly $-\text{CH}_2$ and $\text{N}^+\text{H}_3\text{COO}^-$ group's contribution to V_ϕ^0 are calculated from relation,

$$V_\phi^0(-\text{CH}_2) = V_\phi^0(\text{N}^+\text{H}_3-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2-\text{COO}^-) - V_\phi^0(\text{N}^+\text{H}_3-\text{CH}_2-\text{COO}^-)$$

$$V_\phi^0(\text{N}^+\text{H}_3\text{COO}^-) = V_\phi^0(\text{N}^+\text{H}_3-\text{CH}_2-\text{COOH}) - V_\phi^0(-\text{CH}_2)$$

The values are given in Table 2. These values have been used to calculate limiting apparent transfer molar volumes ($V_\phi^0(\text{tr})$) of amino acids from relation,

$$V_\phi^0(\text{tr}) = V_\phi^0 [(\text{water} + \text{urea}) - \text{water}] \quad (8)$$

This proves that urea composition strengthens the acid interactions with itself and weaken urea-urea with acids and

Table 2. Molal volumes for amino acids fitted to linear regression equation and $2V_{AAU}$ and $3V_{AAUU}$ constants of regression of $V_{\phi}^0(\text{tr})/m_U$ (transfer molar volume) against urea molality. AA stands for amino acids

T (K)	m_U in kg mol^{-1}	V_{ϕ}^0 $\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$	A	Gly in water + urea			$2V_{AA}$	$3V_{AAUU}m_U$
				$V_{\phi}^0(\text{tr})$	$V_{\phi}^0(\text{tr})/m_U$			
288.15	1.1535	43.92 (± 0.12)	0.68	1.43	1.24	0.95 (± 0.03)	-0.16 (± 0.01)	
	2.9039	44.35 (± 0.06)	0.78	1.86	0.64	2.38 (± 0.02)	-0.41 (± 0.02)	
	5.0281	45.35 (± 0.09)	0.50	2.87	0.57	4.12 (± 0.02)	-0.70 (± 0.02)	
	7.0102	46.05 (± 0.10)	0.49	3.57	0.51	5.74 (± 0.05)	-0.98 (± 0.02)	
298.15	0.9900	44.18 (± 0.12)	0.42	0.92	0.93	0.59 (± 0.06)	-0.10 (± 0.01)	
	3.0619	44.80 (± 0.11)	0.42	1.54	0.50	1.83 (± 0.03)	-0.31 (± 0.02)	
	5.8600	45.68 (± 0.10)	0.40	2.43	0.41	3.51 (± 0.02)	-0.60 (± 0.01)	
	7.0013	46.32 (± 0.11)	0.40	3.06	0.44	4.19 (± 0.03)	-0.72 (± 0.02)	
308.15	1.0000	44.23 (± 0.09)	0.92	0.63	0.63	0.28 (± 0.03)	0.04 (± 0.02)	
	3.0893	46.14 (± 0.06)	0.29	2.54	0.82	0.88 (± 0.04)	0.12 (± 0.02)	
	5.8270	46.14 (± 0.08)	0.28	2.54	0.44	1.65 (± 0.03)	0.23 (± 0.03)	
	7.0021	46.89 (± 0.07)	0.28	3.30	0.47	1.98 (± 0.04)	0.27 (± 0.05)	
				DL-ala in water + urea				
288.15	1.0452	60.49 (± 0.08)	0.70	0.60	0.57	0.37 (± 0.05)	-0.05 (± 0.03)	
	3.0173	61.07 (± 0.06)	0.74	1.18	0.39	1.06 (± 0.03)	-0.13 (± 0.02)	
	5.0426	61.36 (± 0.11)	0.72	1.47	0.29	1.77 (± 0.06)	-0.23 (± 0.02)	
	7.0201	61.84 (± 0.12)	0.72	1.95	0.28	2.46 (± 0.04)	-0.31 (± 0.03)	
298.15	0.9160	61.22 (± 0.13)	0.94	0.69	0.75	0.45 (± 0.03)	-0.09 (± 0.04)	
	3.0664	61.26 (± 0.13)	1.08	0.73	0.24	1.49 (± 0.06)	-0.30 (± 0.03)	
	5.0261	61.90 (± 0.12)	1.15	1.37	0.27	2.45 (± 0.02)	-0.50 (± 0.02)	
	6.9989	62.11 (± 0.07)	1.15	1.58	0.23	3.41 (± 0.03)	-0.69 (± 0.03)	
308.15	1.1145	61.62 (± 0.09)	0.61	0.35	0.31	0.24 (± 0.04)	-0.05 (± 0.02)	
	3.0803	61.68 (± 0.08)	0.31	0.41	0.13	0.66 (± 0.02)	-0.13 (± 0.03)	
	5.0982	61.75 (± 0.07)	0.56	0.48	0.09	1.10 (± 0.02)	-0.21 (± 0.04)	
	7.0004	61.81 (± 0.08)	0.56	0.54	0.08	1.51 (± 0.02)	-0.29 (± 0.04)	
				β -ala in water + urea				
288.15	1.0180	59.60 (± 0.08)	0.20	2.12	2.08	1.36 (± 0.03)	-0.27 (± 0.03)	
	3.0041	59.72 (± 0.06)	0.22	2.24	0.75	4.01 (± 0.04)	-0.80 (± 0.05)	
	5.0261	61.90 (± 0.06)	1.15	4.42	0.88	6.72 (± 0.03)	-1.34 (± 0.02)	
	7.0001	62.70 (± 0.11)	1.15	5.22	0.75	9.35 (± 0.03)	-1.87 (± 0.03)	
298.15	0.9951	59.67 (± 0.07)	0.25	0.96	0.96	0.61 (± 0.03)	-0.10 (± 0.03)	
	3.0270	60.27 (± 0.11)	0.51	1.56	0.51	1.84 (± 0.03)	-0.30 (± 0.03)	
	4.9205	60.83 (± 0.06)	0.11	2.12	0.43	2.99 (± 0.05)	-0.48 (± 0.04)	
	7.0001	61.44 (± 0.08)	0.11	2.73	0.39	4.26 (± 0.01)	-0.48 (± 0.05)	
308.15	1.0443	60.32 (± 0.07)	0.39	1.26	1.21	0.88 (± 0.10)	-0.19 (± 0.03)	
	2.9570	60.29 (± 0.08)	0.50	1.23	0.42	2.48 (± 0.03)	-0.53 (± 0.04)	
	5.4929	60.94 (± 0.08)	0.27	1.88	0.34	4.60 (± 0.03)	-0.98 (± 0.04)	
	7.0015	61.07 (± 0.06)	0.14	2.02	0.29	5.87 (± 0.03)	-1.25 (± 0.02)	

temperature weaken the intermolecular forces between the molecules. The V_{ϕ}^0 values of glycine and urea⁶⁻⁸ for water, and of glycine for urea⁴ data²⁵ show close agreement with earlier results^{4,6,7}. Linearly increase V_{ϕ}^0 of systems with concentrations is seen but an increase for aqueous urea is found less than glycine however its values are larger than glycine by 1.65 $\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$ at 288.15 K. Likewise V_{ϕ}^0 values of amino acids with composition for aqueous urea with concentration increase linearly (Fig. 3) at each K. Perhaps urea due to amino ($-\text{NH}_2$) and ketonic ($>\text{C}=\text{O}$) polar groups develop stronger interactions with the dipoles of water than of glycine and denotes that these groups decrease an electrostriction of water by causing larger cohesive forces on hydrated water. Similarly $-\text{N}^+\text{H}_3$ and $-\text{COO}^-$ dipoles of glycine have larger difference in their electron density that causes difference in

their polarity and trigger stronger interactions with water resulting more and more shrinkage in molar volumes. However such shrinkage for urea seems less due to an element of symmetry introduced in the molecule by two $-\text{NH}_2$ groups at both sides of $>\text{CO}$ group. Although an electron density on amino and ketonic groups keep shifting from one to another, probably it could be rationalized to the fact that urea shows more structure breaking action⁸ on water than that of glycine. Therefore urea causes stronger interactions with water and influence an interaction of acids in aqueous solutions and confirms that glycine-glycine interaction decrease cohesive forces of glycine-water that expand molar volume of glycine by ± 0.56 as compared to $\pm 0.35 \text{ cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$ of urea at each K. In case of urea, it seems that urea-urea interactions do not bring much effect in V_{ϕ}^0

Table 3. -CH₂- and N⁺H₃COO⁻ group contribution to apparent molar volumes of acid in systems

$V_{\phi}^0(-CH_2)$ DL-alanine at 288.15 and 303.15 K are reported 16.10 and 16.30 cm³ mol⁻¹

K	V_{ϕ}^0 (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)				Contribution to V_{ϕ}^0 (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)				
	Glycine		β -Alanine		-CH ₂ -		N ⁺ H ₃ COO ⁻		CH ₂
	w+u	w	w+u	w	w+u	w	w+u	w	Lit.* in w
288.15	43.40	42.50	58.68	57.48	15.28	14.98	28.12	27.52	16.10
298.15	43.78	43.33	59.38	58.71	15.60	15.38	28.18	27.95	
303.15									16.30
308.15	44.26	43.85	60.06	59.06	15.80	15.21	28.46	28.64	

Abbreviations : w and u designate water and urea.

* Ref. 21.

Fig. 2. Y-axis V_{ϕ}^0 (tr). [V_{ϕ}^0 (tr) = V_{ϕ}^0 (water + urea) - V_{ϕ}^0 (water) in cm³ mol⁻¹ and X-axis urea molality in mol kg⁻¹ solvent.

(tr) values and proves that water-urea forces are stronger and added urea may facilitate urea-urea interactions. But about ± 0.05 cm³ mol⁻¹ in V_{ϕ}^0 with about 0.50 mol kg⁻¹ of it proves that urea-urea interaction are weaker than of water-urea which could be attributed to the dissimilar dipoles. Therefore the V_{ϕ}^0 (tr) of acids with respect to composition of urea is evaluated from relation,

$$V_{\phi}^0(\text{tr})_{\text{mu}} = V_{\phi}^0((n) m_U \rightarrow (n + 2)m_U) \quad (9)$$

Here ((n) m_U → (n + 2)m_U) are 1 to 3, 3 to 5 and 5 to 7 mol kg⁻¹ urea solution. In general an ± 0.71 cm³ mol⁻¹ in V_{ϕ}^0 (tr)_{mu} with composition of urea at each K for glycine and DL-alanine indicate that urea composition behaves as structure breaker of water because Van der Waals forces of

Fig. 3. Y-axis volumes in cm³ mol⁻¹ and X-axis temperature in Kelvin. Figs. a and b represent an influence of electrostriction, and c and d contribution of -CH₂- and -N⁺H₃COO⁻ for V_{ϕ}^0 .

water decrease and water exert less cohesive forces on acid molecules. But this value for β -alanine is found to be ± 1.03 cm³ mol⁻¹ at 288.15 and ± 0.59 and ± 0.281 cm³ mol⁻¹ for 298.15 and 308.15 K. However the V_{ϕ}^0 (tr) with composition of urea are found in order of 7 > 5 > 3 > 1 with an average value 1 to 3 cm³ mol⁻¹ for glycine and DL-alanine and about 1 to 5 cm³ mol⁻¹ for β -alanine. This confirms that β -position of -N⁺H₃ group develops larger cohesive force on molecule and show larger shrinkage in volume, which decreases considerably with urea composition. And larger increase in V_{ϕ}^0 (tr) is observed for 308.15 K among acids and the V_{ϕ}^0 (tr) for β -alanine is of the order of 2 to 4 cm³ mol⁻¹ which indicates that urea composition has larger influence on β -alanine-water interactions than DL-alanine. It seems

that urea might be interacting with water which is sandwiched in hydrophobic sphere of $-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-$ and its removal causes larger variation in $V_\phi^0(\text{tr})$ and further larger increase in $V_\phi^0(\text{tr})$ is seen at 308.15 K. This reflects that thermal energy weakens hydrogen bonding of water and $V_\phi^0(\text{tr}) = V_\phi^0((n)m_U \rightarrow (n+2)m_U)$ are lower than the values obtained with respect to temperature by an average value of $\pm 0.75 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$. This proves that state of thermal energy dominants over an influence of urea composition which brings about an average increase in V_ϕ^0 of acid for example ± 0.71 for glycine, ± 0.72 DL-alanine and $\pm 0.63 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ for β -alanine. Comparatively the V_ϕ^0 values of β -alanine are lower and DL-alanine by about ± 0.89 however it slightly decrease with urea composition but increases with K. These variations could be attributed to the forces of attraction between $-\text{N}^+\text{H}_3$ and $-\text{COO}^-$ of β -alanine due to a distance between them by $-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-$ as compared to DL-alanine. It seems that such position of polar groups shrinks volume and enhance it could be concluded that β -alanine is stronger structure breaker than of DL- α -alanine and urea too. Also that the hydrophilic interactions between water and β -alanine are stronger and distance by $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2-$ between groups develops stronger intramolecular force in molecule. So it substantially decrease an electrostriction of water as this force attacks the dipoles of water and breaks them by weakening intermolecular forces of water molecules. And seems to squeeze out the bulk water from the cage surrounding $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2-$ through hydrophobic interactions. Thereby removal of bulk water causes comparatively much volume decrease than of hydrophilic. Reportedly the lower $V_\phi^0(\text{tr})$ values for DL- α -alanine with respect to urea at each K could be explained as bulk water caging CH_3CH_2- is not removed out on interaction between DL- α -alanine-DL- α -alanine. Infact it is seen that due to an attraction between polar groups at one end of DL- α -alanine, the hydrophilic interactions are strengthened.

For amino acids positive values of $V_\phi^0(\text{tr})$ indicates that acid interactions decrease electrostriction of water as well as aqueous urea solutions and seems to weaken cohesive forces associated with acid-water or acid-urea interactions. An increase in $V_\phi^0(\text{tr})$ with composition of urea also indicates that it further interact with water molecules instead of acid's. Probably a decrease in dipole moment of water results less forces between acid-water so a net increase in $V_\phi^0(\text{tr})$ is reported with temperature. It reflects that thermal energy of solvation behaves as structure breaker weakening cohesive force thereby acid molecule mark slightly larger expansion in volume than urea.

A decrease in electrostriction of water due to localized N^+H_3 and COO^- groups and also urea-urea interactions with concentration seem responsible for an increase in vol-

umes of acids and result into positive $V_\phi^0(\text{tr})$ values of acid systems at each K (Table 2). But transfer values are higher for β -alanine than DL- α -alanine for similar compositions of urea at each temperature⁶ (Table 2 and Fig. 1). The values of $\Delta V_\phi^0(\text{tr}) [=V_\phi^0(\text{tr}) \text{ alanine} - V_\phi^0(\text{tr}) \text{ Gly}]$ are found by $\pm 0.54 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ for DL-alanine but for β -alanine is ± 0.69 . The $V_\phi^0(\text{tr})$ value for DL- α -alanine as compared to glycine with difference of CH_3 group was found to be $-1.14 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ at 298.15 K and these values for 6 m urea⁹ are found in close agreement. However larger $V_\phi^0(\text{tr})$ values for β -alanine have been attributed to an electrostatic interactions between functional groups placed apart by a distance of $-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-$ chain. The magnitude of $V_\phi^0(\text{tr})$ values remain almost same for each molal composition of urea at each K and with composition of urea a slight increase in values is found. Although increase $V_\phi^0(\text{tr})$ values for acids is noticed greater than urea with larger values for β -alanine and depicts that the strength of molecular interactions comparatively stronger for β -alanine. Likewise the $V_\phi^0(\text{tr})$ values of methylene ($-\text{CH}_2-$) groups have been found similar to the values reported elsewhere⁹. As the molecular interactions govern the over all behavior of molecule in solutions responsible for magnitude of molal volume, therefore the values of $[V_\phi^0(\text{tr})(\beta\text{-ala}) - V_\phi^0(\text{tr})(\text{AA})]$ in $\text{cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ are estimated from the contributions¹⁰ of four volume factors as eq. (10),

$$V_\phi^0 = (V_{\phi_{\text{vow}}} + V_\phi) + (V_{\phi_{\text{U}}} + V_{\phi_{\text{h}}}) \quad (10)$$

where, $V_{\phi_{\text{vow}}}$ is an intrinsic or van der Waals volume generated due to residual forces on the molecule, V_ϕ the void volume, $V_{\phi_{\text{U}}}$ the contribution from solute-solute-solvent and solute-cosolute-solvent interactions and $V_{\phi_{\text{h}}}$ from the hydrophobic hydration. Taking $(V_{\phi_{\text{vow}}} + V_\phi)$ to be the same⁸ for water and urea systems, therefore, the changes in $(V_{\phi_{\text{U}}} + V_{\phi_{\text{h}}})$ should explain the observed trends in V_ϕ^0 or $V_\phi^0(\text{tr})$. The $(V_{\phi_{\text{U}}} + V_{\phi_{\text{h}}})$ of acids for water and urea systems is estimated from relations (11) and (12),

$$(V_{\phi_{\text{vow}}} + V_\phi)_{\text{w}} = V_{\phi_{\text{AW}}} + V_{\phi_{\text{ww}}} \quad (11)$$

$$(V_{\phi_{\text{U}}} + V_{\phi_{\text{h}}})_{\text{w+U}} = V_{\phi_{\text{UA}}} + V_{\phi_{\text{UU}}} - V_{\phi_{\text{UW}}} + V_{\phi_{\text{WW}}} \quad (12)$$

The $V_{\phi_{\text{UA}}}$, $V_{\phi_{\text{UU}}}$, $V_{\phi_{\text{UW}}}$ and $V_{\phi_{\text{WW}}}$ are the contributions from urea-amino acid, urea-urea, urea-water and dipolar (water-water) interactions respectively, hence $V_\phi^0(\text{tr})$ [eq. (12)–eq. (11)] after canceling out $V_{\phi_{\text{WW}}}$ a common term gives relation as,

$$V_\phi^0(\text{tr}) = V_{\phi_{\text{UA}}} + V_{\phi_{\text{UU}}} - V_{\phi_{\text{UW}}} - V_{\phi_{\text{AW}}} \quad (13)$$

Here, the positive $V_{\phi_{\text{UA}}}$ may be due to a predominance of urea-polar group over urea-nonpolar group interactions and

also due to a decrease in electrostriction of water by urea. Notably a decrease in $V_{\phi UW}$ and increase in $V_{\phi UU}$, and assumed constancy of $V_{\phi WW}$ values jointly explain an increase in V_{ϕ}^0 [or positive V_{ϕ}^0 (tr)] with urea concentration. However, a gradual decrease in $(V_{\phi UU} - V_{\phi UW})$ with urea concentration is reported and seen responsible for leveling off of the $V_{\phi}^0 - m_U [V_{\phi}^0$ (tr) - $m_U]$ curves.

An increase in V_{ϕ}^0 or V_{ϕ}^0 (tr) with temperature is contributed from an increase in $V_{\phi UA}$ due to an increased thermal energy of water. This effect is also functional for electrostricted regions of zwitterions and decrease in $-V_{\phi UW}$ due to the favored urea-urea interactions. While the contribution from changes in $-V_{\phi WW}$ can be taken as relatively small¹¹ therefore the V_{ϕ}^0 (tr) on the other hand decreases with temperature (Table 2) which can be rationalized by considering the temperature coefficients of various terms contributing to V_{ϕ}^0 (tr) urea as eq. (12). A trend for V_{ϕ}^0 (tr) values converges at common point at around higher urea concentration (Fig. 2) and $-CH_2$ and $N^+H_3CO^-$ group's contribution^{29,30} to V_{ϕ}^0 for glycine (Figs. 3c and d) is found greater for water than that of urea systems. It could be attributed to fact that the $V_{\phi AW}$ for acids arose due to the dipolar centers causing electrostriction but urea molecules are seen to affect amino acid-water and water-water interactions by causing a slight decrease in an electrostriction of amino acid molecules in water. Comparatively the higher values of V_{ϕ}^0 for DL- α -alanine are observed than β -alanine in accordance to the greater electrostriction (elect) of β -alanine in solution and is evaluated from following relation,

$$V_{\phi}^0 \text{ elect (amino acids)} = V_{\phi}^0 \text{ elect (urea + water)} - V_{\phi}^0 \text{ elect (water)}$$

It is evident that the position of polar groups, which are pole apart by $-CH_2-CH_2-$ to each other in the β -alanine molecule causes stronger electrostriction squeezing out some of the water molecules from hydration sphere of β -alanine leading to a decrease in V_{ϕ}^0 .

Experimental

Glycine, DL- α -alanine and β -alanine (A.R., Sigma) and urea (B.D.H.) were used after drying overnight at 373.15 K and then vacuo over phosphorous pentoxide (P_2O_5) at 298.15 K for a 24 h. Triple-distilled water with addition of alkaline permanganate and deionized by passing through two Cole-Parmer mixed bed ion exchanger columns and of conductivity less than $6 \times 10^{-5} \Omega^{-1} m^{-1}$ was used for solu-

tions afresh by weight with Mettler balance (1×10^{-5} g) model H51AR. Prior to measurements the solutions were thermostated at least for 45 min.

Solutions have been injected into a double walled U shaped borosilicate sample tube of instrument and gas of high thermal conductivity was filled in the double walled jacket around the tube for rapid thermal equilibrium of solutions. This tube was made of quartz glass that works based on oscillation and referred to as oscillation tube (OT), the oscillations were related to the density of solution for measurements at prescribed temperature. For temperature control an electronic thermostat was attached with an instrument for determination of temperature of solution in OT. From thermostat a sensor encapsulated in the form of capillary of 2 mm diameter was injected to the jacket filled with gas. Also for density measurements an analog signal generated in synchronism with an oscillating sample tube was transmitted into an electronic processing unit (DMA60) of instrument. There were several options in-made with instrument for selection of pulse of oscillations of OT, these are 1000, 2000, 5000, 10000, 20000 and 50000 but to optimize the time of measurement and accuracy the 10000 pulse time was chosen for present work. After recording pulse time for each sample, OT was washed out with solvent and dried completely with acetone and rinsed with the solutions, which is under measurement. For this purpose a thermistor is fitted with a built-in air pump with sintered glass filter for drying the tube and for consecutive measurements the temperature of the tube was maintained using a hotpack circulating thermostat bath with an electronic thermoregulator. The temperature was displayed with digital thermometer fitted with Anton Paar to $\pm 0.01^\circ C$, it can only measure temperature from 278.15 to 298.15 K. Therefore 308.15 K was obtained by putting calibrated two Beckman thermometers in the bath of it where the first Beckman was calibrated at 298.15 K with Anton Paar unit, notably for 298.15 K, Hg point of Beckman was kept at the lower level. This Beckman was then kept in densimeter's bath keeping the knob of variac of thermoregulator at higher potential corresponding to 308.15 K.

The calibration of Beckman was checked with Hicks thermometer several times to remove any discrepancy and after an adjustment of temperatures.

Conclusion :

The values and variations in values of apparent molar volumes, transfer apparent molar volumes and interaction coefficients of aqueous systems prove that acids and urea behave as structure breakers at chosen temperatures. The

concentrations and temperature of the systems have been observed to strengthen an effect on water structure. Likewise a larger overlapping in β -alanine due to greater electrostriction produce lower volumes than that α -counterpart.

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